

Development of colorimetric methods for determination of total phenolic content in tea

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In this work, a colorimetric method has been developed utilizing a smartphone and a home-office scanner to determine total phenolic content of three types of commercially available teas. The colorimetric determination relied on the measurement of the aqueous blue product yielded from the Folin-Ciocalteu phenolic assay. The smartphone device layout consisted of a light box and an iPhone 7 plus. The images were processed using the application, ColorAssist. The smartphone results yielded a total phenolic content for Baimon tea, Taiwan tea, and Black tea of 3.78, 23.83, and 40.91 mg GAE/g tea, respectively. The scanner device layout consisted of an office scanner and a 96-well microplate. The images were processed using ImageJ. The scanner results gave a total phenolic content for Baimon tea, Taiwan tea, and Black tea of 5.55, 15.27, and 42.27 mg GAE/g tea, respectively. The results obtained from the colorimetric methods were comparable to those from the spectrophotometric plate reader used as a traditional method. The total phenolic content obtained from the spectrophotometric microplate method for Baimon tea, Taiwan tea, and Black tea were 4.65, 20.83, and 36.35 mg GAE/g tea, respectively. These methods can provide convenient, fast and efficient measurement compared to traditional methods.

1. Introduction

Tea (*Camellia sinensis*) is considered to be one of the most widely consumed beverages in the world. This is not only due to its delightful flavors but also its potential for health benefits. Tea is recognized to contain abundant bioactive compounds such as catechin, and other polyphenols, functioning as antioxidants which are believed to be responsible for maintaining optimal health.¹

Determination methods such as high-performance liquid chromatograph (HPLC) and liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS) are widely used for developing phenolic profiles of tea.^{1,2} These methods are great for providing comprehensive data with which specific compounds can be identified but require specific laboratories and trained personnel. Spectrophotometric methods based on the Folin-Ciocalteu assay are used for screening high total phenolic content (TPC) in tea samples.^{1,3} However,

spectrophotometers are not always available in rural and resource limited settings.

With advanced technology in electronics nowadays, devices such as digital cameras, smartphones, laptops, and scanners, are more readily available at moderate costs; this further enhances accessibility of alternative analysis tools. These electronic devices can be used to perform a traditional spectrophotometric measurement through a colorimetric analysis using digital imaging.⁴

In this work, colorimetric methods using a smartphone and home-office scanner were developed to determine the total phenolic content in tea. The method is based on the measurement of the amount of resulting blue product obtained from the Folin-Ciocalteu assay. A conventional spectrophotometric plate reader was used to validate the developed methods.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Chemicals

All chemicals used in this work were analytical grade and deionized water was used to prepare the solutions. Gallic acid (98.0%), Folin-Ciocalteu's phenol reagent, and sodium carbonate (99%) were purchased from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany).

2.2 Sample preparation

Three commercial tea samples, including Baimon tea, Taiwan tea, and Black tea, available in the local department stores in Maejo, Chiang Mai, Thailand, were used to perform the phenolic determination. The preparation of tea extracts was carried out using the method described by Kodama *et al.*⁵ with some modifications. Each tea sample (0.07500 g) was extracted by immersion in 100 mL of hot distilled water (93 °C) for 5 minutes. Then, the extract was removed through filtration. After cooling to room temperature, the volume of the extract was adjusted to 100 mL.

2.3 Total phenolic content

The total phenolic content was determined based on the Folin-Ciocalteu assay.⁵ In brief, 100 μ L of the standard/sample was added to 2.5 mL of the Folin-Ciocalteu reagent (1/10 v/v). The mixture was incubated for 2 minutes followed by the addition of 2.0 mL of sodium carbonate (7.5% w/v). The solution was mixed thoroughly and incubated in the dark at room temperature for two hours before it was transferred onto a 96-well microplate. The determination of total phenolic content was performed using three separate analysis methods: smartphone, office scanner, and spectrophotometric plate reader. The total phenolic content was quantified using gallic acid as a phenolic standard and expressed as mg of gallic acid equivalent per one gram of tea sample (mg GAE / g tea).

2.4 Determination of total phenolic content

The color intensity of the blue product from the assay depended on and correlated to the concentration of the polyphenols in the samples. The smartphone and scanner detection methods were based on the measurements of these color intensities of the samples as presented as RGB (red-green-blue) values. For the smartphone method, the color intensities of the samples were measured and quantitated as RGB values using an iPhone 7 plus (Apple, USA) and a commercially available mobile phone application, ColorAssist (FTLapps, Inc., USA). A simple homebuilt wooden box (110 \times 255 \times 170 mm), consisting of two arrays of bright LEDs (LED2835, Cree, USA) as a wide-spectrum light source, was used as a tool to regulate lighting conditions throughout experiments. For the scanner method, the microplate images were acquired and recorded in JPEG format with 600 dpi using a color scanner (Epson L365, Japan). A commercially available, open source, image-processing program, ImageJ (NIH, USA) was used to extract the RGB color intensity values from the scanned digital images. The conventional spectrophotometric microplate reader (Spectrostar Nano, BMG Labtech, Germany) was used as a validation method and the absorbance of the blue product was measured at 765 nm.

2.5 Calibration curves

The total phenolic content of samples was estimated using gallic acid standard curves from each detection method. The standard curves were generated using concentration of the standards plotted against its correlated absorbance values. The absorbance values of the spectrophotometric method were directly given of the instrument. The absorbance (A) values of colorimetric smartphone and scanner methods can be calculated from the RGB values using the

formula, which is defined as $A = -\log(I/I_0)$, where I is the color intensity of testing solution and I_0 is the color intensity of the blank solution.⁶

3. Results & Discussion

3.1 Selection of calibration curves

Calibration curves for the smartphone and scanner were created using six standard solutions of gallic acid in a concentration range from 0 to 100 mg L⁻¹ as shown in Figure 1A and B.

The linear regression of the smartphone RGB color channels yielded a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.9993, 0.9959 and 0.9897 respectively. The linear regression of the scanner RGB color channels yielded a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.9991, 0.9537 and 0.9002 respectively. The red (R) color channel was selected for both methods for use throughout this work owing to its high correlation coefficient. Figure 2 displays the calibration curves of the two colorimetric methods compared to the curve from the traditional spectrophotometric plate reader method. Adequate linearity is noted in all three methods.

Figure 1. A. Calibration curve for the smartphone RGB absorbance for gallic acid standards. B. Calibration curve for the scanner RGB absorbance for gallic acid standards.

Figure 2. Calibration curves for the traditional spectrophotometric plate reader method compared to the curves from the selected red color channel in both the smartphone and scanner methods.

3.2 Analytical method validation

Analytical validation of the three methods was obtained by first preparing known concentrations of gallic acid solutions (0, 30, 50, 70, and 90 ppm). The methods were carried out and the resulting absorbance values were obtained. The regression equations from the calibration curves were then used to determine the

concentration of the gallic acid in each sample. The results are shown in Figure 3. A perfect correlation is expected to yield a coefficient of determination of 1. The plate reader, smartphone, and scanner methods yielded R^2 values of 0.9821, 0.9926, and 0.9967 respectively.

Figure 3. Correlation between known concentrations of gallic acid and concentrations determined from the gallic acid standard calibration curves.

3.3 Total phenolic content in tea

Determination of the total phenolic content of the three teas was carried out using a smartphone, a scanner, and a traditional plate reader. The smartphone results yielded a total phenolic content for Baimon tea, Taiwan tea, and Black tea of 3.78, 23.83, and 40.91 mg GAE/g tea, respectively. The scanner results gave a total phenolic content for Baimon tea, Taiwan tea, and Black tea of 5.55, 15.27, and 42.27 mg GAE/g tea, respectively. The total phenolic content obtained from the spectrophotometric microplate method for Baimon tea, Taiwan tea, and Black tea were 4.65, 20.83, and 36.35 mg GAE/g tea, respectively.

Figure 4. Total phenolic content (n=1) in three commercially available teas obtained from department stores in Chiang Mai, Thailand. Please note that no statistical method was employed to compare the results.

4. Conclusion

Two colorimetric methods for determination of phenolic content in teas were presented. One method employed the use of a smartphone camera and the other method employed the use of a home office scanner. Overall, these methods provided for low cost, efficient, and accurate determinations of phenolic content in teas. These methods favor convenient and rapid determination of phenolic content.

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